

Impulse as a Physical Measure and the Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

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Quantum mechanics is concerned with measurement and we suggest that in a bound problem impulses due to momentum are the form of measurement which occurs in x space. The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, which is also the free particle relativistic or nonrelativistic action with $v = x/t$, associates energy $= p^2/2m$ with time and p with x . Creating eigenvalue equations yields $i\hbar d/dt \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt)$ and $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. P (momentum) is associated with physical impulses and with its own two dimensional probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$. E is associated with t and has its own distribution in time $\exp(-iEt)$ which implies that the same E holds for each x point without any notion of x probability associated with it.

In classical physics, a momentum p exists in a tiny dx ($dx \rightarrow 0$). For $\exp(ipx)$, a p impulse may occur within \hbar/p with different probabilities, so one cannot restrict the measurement of p to a tiny dx unless dx is of the order of \hbar/p . Nevertheless energy exists at all x points. Given that p measurements occur through specific impulses at different x points with $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities, one must calculate an average energy using $\{\sum \text{over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\}$ using the probability associated with the measurement of p in space i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This adds to $V(x)$ to yield a constant E at each x point.

We suggest that weighted $\exp(ipx)$ s are used to calculate average energy at each x , because it is through impulse measurements that one determines p at different x values and hence the average energy. One may note that one does not calculate $\{\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \ p\} / \{\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\}$. An impulse hit is associated with a certain probability and this measurement in x yields information about the corresponding energy $p^2/2m$. Each impulse hit also yields information about a time probability $\exp(-i p t / 2m)$, but only if the particle is knocked out of the bound system i.e. only if $p^2/2m$ is the only energy present, which is not the case for a single particle bound system.

Classical Physics

Classical physics assumes that one knows $x(t)$ and hence $v(t)$ or $v(x)$, $p(x)$, $p(x)p(x)/2m$. In other words, one may presumably measure all of these within a tiny dx , miniscule compared to the overall length in the system. One may ask, however, what specific measurements are made?

The one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem suggests that impulse measurements associated with p (momentum) and a corresponding probability $\exp(ipx)$ are the physical basis of the reflection-refraction interactions. We suggest, as done in previous notes, that this same impulse is the basis of measurements of p in the quantum single particle bound state. If one could decisively measure p within dx (as $dx \rightarrow 0$), there would be a $p(x)$ as well as $p(x)p(x)/2m$ at each x . The question we suggest is that one may not be able to measure p decisively at a specific x .

Classical Action

The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ ((1)) is also the free particle relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action with $v=x/t$. As we have argued before, A separates t and x treating them as independent and associating E with t and p with x . If $v=x/t$ then one has p at a specific x and also a corresponding $E=pp/2m$ i.e. the classical scenario.

We have suggested before that one may create eigenvalue equations based on A i.e.:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2b))$$

In other words, there are two two-dimensional probability schemes, one in time associated with E (an E which exists at all x points), and a second in x linked to p . P (momentum), we argue, is linked with the physical measurement of impulses, but this measurement does not occur at a single x , rather there is a two-dimensional probability scheme over a range of \hbar/p . In other words, the classical notion of p being measured in dx does not hold unless dx is of the order of \hbar/p .

Quantum mechanics is based on measurement and so one has to take seriously the probability associated with the measurement of p i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. It is the measurement of p , we argue, based on $\exp(ipx)$ which yields information about $pp/2m$. Thus even if one wishes to calculate average energy, which is the same at each x , one needs to use the probability scheme of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the impulse scheme because this is the physical measurement which occurs in the system.

Given that a specific p cannot be decisively measured at a point x , one must consider different p values with their respective $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities and calculate an average kinetic energy. This, when added to $V(x)$, yields energy which is the same at each x . It is this total energy which is associated with a probability distribution $\exp(-i E_n t)$ unless one knocks out a particle during an impulse measurement in which case one only has $pp/2m$ and the corresponding $\exp(-i ppt/2m)$.

Thus considerations of the physical measurement of p and its unusual $\exp(ipx)$ probability form govern the calculation of average energy:

$$\left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

Knowledge of p and x

Given that a single p cannot decisively be determined to be at x (i.e. there are probabilities for it to be anywhere within a wavelength), one needs to average over various p values, but this occurs for all x points i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ exists in all of space. Thus one argues that given a p value, one does not know where the particle is in space.

What happens at high energies, however, is that $\hbar/prms(x)$ may become small and fit within a dx which is tiny compared to the system length. In such a case, $prms(x)$ is a number at x which equals a specific momentum whose wavelength fits within dx . As a result, one can measure p decisively at “ x ” if the spread dx is considered to represent x . In such a case, one

does not need to average over various p values. A physical impulse measurement occurs within dx and determines $pp/2m$ at x (i.e. within dx).

This scenario, however, suggests a transition from quantum mechanics (impulse measurement spread picture) to a classical one which is governed by an acceptable width dx . In principle, one may apply a quantum bound state calculation to all energy levels, but this calculation uses the measurement of impulse to calculate average energy. If the impulse measurement occurs within dx , one has $prms(x)prms(x)/2m$ as energy within dx and this corresponds to the impulse measurement of a single p with the value $prms(x)$ at x .

Issue of the Wavefunction

$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ represents a quantum wavefunction such that $\text{density}(x) = W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state. As energy levels become very high, peaks and troughs of $W(x)$ and hence peaks of $W(x)W(x)$ become very narrow. If one coarse grains and accepts a p impulse measurement to be within dx , as one does not have enough resolution to measure within dx , it seems one does not need to worry about the peaks of $W(x)W(x)$, but may use the coarse grained classical view.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is based on measurement. For a single particle bound problem, one must consider what physical measurement occurs in the system. We suggest an impulse measurement based on p (momentum) is key based on the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem. Classically one has the view that one may decisively measure p and $pp/2m$ in a tiny dx such that $dx \rightarrow 0$.

Using the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$, which is the classical relativistic/nonrelativistic action with $v=x/t$, and writing eigenvalue equations leads to nonlocal probabilities in time and space i.e. $i\hbar/dt \exp(-iEt)$. This suggests that if momentum impulse measurements occur in space they exist in a range \hbar/p . Thus one cannot decisively measure p within dx unless it is of the order of \hbar/p . If it is not, one must consider an average of p values with their corresponding $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities to calculate an average energy at a point x as p impulse hits are the physical manner in which p is determined. This leads to the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } pp/2m \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E_n$$

As energy levels become very high $prms(x)$ fits within a dx , i.e. a tiny length compared to the overall system length. If it is assumed that one has no resolution within dx , one may decisively assign a p (with value of $prms(x)$) to dx such that a physical impulse hit occurs within dx and establishes both the values of p and $pp/2m$ in dx . In such a case, one no longer needs to average over different p values in this coarse grained view.